

Query Log Analysis on an Academic Search Portal for Economics and Business Studies

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1. Introduction

User behavior on search engines has been analyzed based on data from search queries (Kacprzak et al., 2017) and click behavior (Barifah & Landoni, 2019). The goal has been to describe the typologies of users and in part also to make inferences about dimensions that are not observed in the log data, such as goals, strategies, and preferences (Baeza-Yates et al., 2006; Schultheiß et al., 2020). We analyze click patterns conditional on query topics. Our aim is to deepen the understanding of how users behave in their formulation of search queries and in their interaction with the search portal EconBiz.

EconBiz is targeted towards an educational and academic audience in management and economics and covers around 12.9 million entries, such as journal articles, book chapters, working papers, monographs and conference proceedings (Nickerson & Schmidt, 2023). Our data source for quantitative analysis consists of log files, which include search queries and click data in form of actions from 159,809 sessions from January 2021 until the end of March 2022. The 19 different actions include, for example, using the advanced search or filters or clicking on an outgoing link.

The goal of our investigation is to deepen the understanding of search behavior in the discipline of economics and management along two dimensions. First, we aim to find the main search topics and their distribution across sessions by clustering search queries. Second, we explore the correlation between search topics and clicking behavior to identify possible search types. We ask if and how the click behavior and search topics are related or whether click behavior is uniform across all topics. Additionally, we investigate whether the search sessions that possibly include title searches are followed by a more restricted click behavior than other search queries.

Search queries are summarized by topic clustering via latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) (Blei et al., 2003). LDA creates groups of words based on words that appear together in sessions most frequently. Each group can be interpreted as a topic. Based on our own knowledge of the domain, we aggregated 80 automatically created topics further into 16 overarching topics. Single queries are compared string-wise with the titles of returned results to estimate whether a query includes a publication title, possibly being an indicator for a closed search (Schultheiß et al., 2020). The occurrence of actions is added up to the count per action in each session. We use the statistical measure of mutual information to investigate the correlation between actions within a topic.

Results show that the most prevalent aggregated topics are “business and strategies”, “digitalization and technology” and “workplace”.

It seems straightforward that users click on a search result after submitting a query. Interestingly, for almost every query, at most one document was clicked. Clicking on a search result frequently comes with clicking on the availability button. Users who use a facet are more likely to browse the pages of the search engine results page, perhaps having less “trust bias” (Joachims et al., 2007).

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